

TEACHER EFFECTIVENESS OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN RELATION TO THEIR SENSE OF HUMOUR

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Abstract

Effective teacher is considered to impact not only academic but also social and attitudinal outcomes of students. The question “what makes a teacher effective” has long been searched. Several attempts have been made to measure teacher effectiveness (TE) and the present study is also an attempt in this regard. The present study is aimed at studying Teacher Effectiveness of Secondary School Teachers in relation to their Sense of Humour. To achieve this purpose, Teacher Effectiveness Scale (TES-KU) by Umme Kulsum (2022) and Sense of Humour Scale by Malik & Kapoor (2014) has been used. A sample of 200 teachers was selected by random sampling technique from district Uttarkashi of Uttarakhand. After analysing the data, the researcher found that there is significant difference among the teachers on teacher effectiveness with reference of gender and locality as well as sense of humour found the difference in both areas of teachers. But the correlation is positive.

Keywords: Teacher Effectiveness, Secondary school Teachers, Sense of humour.

1. Introduction

Teacher holds the pivotal position in any education system and the effectiveness of instruction depends mostly on the quality he/she possesses. An effective teacher may be understood as the one, who helps in the development of basic skills, understanding, proper work habits and value judgement. Teacher effectiveness is the degree of success of a teacher in performing instructional and other duties as demanded by the nature of his work.

Teaching needs a person with thirst for knowledge and social service, loyalty, patience and dedication and thus the choice of the right kind of prospective teachers is a must for qualitative growth in secondary education in our nation. The Education Commission Report (1964-66) had also emphasized the role of a teacher in the education process as, “the most important factor contemplated for educational reconstruction is the teacher- his personal qualities, his educational qualification and the place that he occupies in the school as well as in the community.”

Teacher effectiveness can also be measured in terms of factors such as teaching attitude, emotional intelligence, sense of humour etc. Having a decent sense of humour implies that an individual has an amazing gathering of good jokes; he has remembered a substantial number of entertaining stories and therefore can make others snicker at his own account. Thus, the quality teachers not only provide the quality education but also inculcate the set of values in the children. It is the duty of the teacher to provide students with sufficient guidance which in turn helps them in developing a good personality and contribute in the development of the nation.

1.1 Need Of The Study

Teachers are intended to inspire, entertain, and develop creativity, inspire hope and imbibe rules to the learners along with their teaching. Effectiveness of teachers is based on their performance in the classroom setup but which includes the accountability for student learning and to develop humanitarian characteristics. Hence, we should pay more attention towards teacher effectiveness so that the future generation are to be adequately prepared to face the changing time. Secondary school teachers occupy a place of crucial importance. The future of the country inevitably rests on them; it is prominent for them to earn public recognition by their enlightened devoting and professional efficiency.

Therefore, this study would further look over the relationship between the teacher effectiveness and sense of humour. The researcher also endeavours to compare the teacher effectiveness and sense of humour among male & female secondary school teachers. The results will definitely contribute in the field of teaching.

1.2 Review Of Literature

- **Kumari, Meena (2017)** conducted a study on the teacher effectiveness of secondary school teachers in relation to Teaching Competency and Spiritual Intelligence in four districts of Haryana State. The investigator took 400 secondary school teachers, 40 from government school and 40 from private school. The study revealed that government and private school teachers vary significantly in relation to teacher effectiveness and spiritual intelligence. Also, male and female teachers were found different in terms of teacher effectiveness and spiritual intelligence.
- **Devi and Talukdar (2018)** studied the effectiveness of college teachers in relation to their mental health in respect of their gender (male and female) and locality (rural & urban). The sample comprised of 272 college teachers of 136 male (68 from Kamrup Rural and 68 from Kamrup Metro) and 136 female (68 from Kamrup Rural and 68 from Kamrup Metro) teachers are randomly selected. Results shown that there is positive correlation is found between mental health and teaching effectiveness of college teachers. It is found that significant difference prevails in mental health of teachers in college belonging to rural and urban areas which directly affect the effectiveness of the teachers.
- **Kaur, Harsangeet (2019)** conducted a study on teacher effectiveness of secondary school teachers in relation to sense of humour, emotional maturity and organizational climate. Descriptive survey method of research was employed on 400 secondary school teachers of Malwa Region of Punjab. Stratified Random Sampling technique was used for the sample. TES by Malik & Kapoor (2014) and Organizational Climate Scale (Singh, 2015) were employed for data collection. Major findings revealed that there exists positive and significant relationship between teacher effectiveness and sense of humour, emotional maturity and organizational climate among secondary school teachers
- **Malik, Umendra (2020)** investigated a study on the sense of humour and TPACK with professional commitment of senior secondary school teachers in overall sample, gender and location. The study was conducted on sample of 200 senior secondary school teachers. The findings showed that there exists positive and significant correlation of sense of humour and TPACK with professional commitment in male and female teachers. Also there exists a

positive and significant correlation of sense of humour and TPACK with professional commitment in both rural & urban male & female teachers.

- **Arya, Indu (2021)** attempted a study on teacher effectiveness and Occupational Stress of senior secondary school teachers of Jaipur. In the present study, 168 senior secondary schools of Jaipur is the universe. Stratified random sampling technique was adopted to choose teachers on the basis of gender and types of school. The results showed that there exists a positive correlation between teacher effectiveness and occupational stress. Also there exist a significant relationship between teacher effectiveness and occupational stress on the basis of gender and type of school.
- **Dhiman, Raj Kumar & Mehta, Arti (2022)** conducted a study on sense of humour among science and non-science background senior secondary teachers in Hamirpur District of Himachal Pradesh. A sample of 100 senior secondary teachers was selected through simple random sampling technique. Thorson and Powell (1993) Multidimensional Sense of Humour Scale (MSHS) was used to collect data. The findings showed that there is no significant difference in sense of humour among science and non-science background senior secondary teachers in Hamirpur District of Himachal Pradesh.
- **Bhatia, Ajay & Mohsin, Farhat (2023)** conducted a study to analyse the relationship between teacher's workplace happiness and their academic performance. The survey was sent out to a total of 124 teachers of Delhi NCR, out of which only 82 responded. Non-probability convenience sampling technique was used for this purpose. The findings showed that there is a significant and positive correlation between Teacher's workplace happiness & academic performance. Also, no significant difference in means was found between male & female teachers, as far as academic performance is considered.
- **Naik, Sanjay (2024)** studied the relationship between teacher effectiveness of secondary school teachers in relation to their occupational stress and job satisfaction. The sample consisted of 60 teachers (30 male and 30 female) and the result indicated a [positive relationship between teacher effectiveness, job satisfaction and occupational stress. While, gender does not appear to influence teacher effectiveness and other variables.
- **Koushik Das & R. Gnanadevan (2025)** investigated the relationship between teacher effectiveness and capacity building of teacher educators. The sample consisted of 260 teacher educators from North 24 Pargana of West Bengal. Results indicated that all the dimensions of teacher effectiveness is significantly correlated with all the dimensions of capacity building.

1.3 Operational Definitions

Teacher Effectiveness

Teacher effectiveness refers to asset of within-person attributes- personality, motivation, beliefs and dispositions that interact with contextual factors (cultural, social, and educational) to influence. It centres on good teaching, possessing appropriate and sufficient knowledge of the subject matter and also allowing the equal participation of the students in the classroom.

Secondary School Teachers

All the teachers teaching at secondary level schools are secondary school teachers.

Sense of Humour

The word "humour" has been derived from the Latin word for "liquid" or "fluid". And the word "sense" insinuates that the person is able to perceive that there is a humour in the situation.

The Oxford English Dictionary described humour as the quality of action, speech, or writing which elicits amusement; eccentric, clever, jesting, comic, humorous imagination or treatment of a topic.

2. Objectives Of The Study

- To find out the relationship between the Teacher Effectiveness of Secondary School Teachers in relation to their Sense of Humour.
- To find out the difference in Teacher Effectiveness of Secondary School Teachers with respect to their gender (male and female).
- To find out the difference in Teacher Effectiveness of Secondary School Teachers with respect to their locality (rural and urban).
- To find out the difference in Sense of Humour of Secondary School Teachers with respect to their gender (male and female).
- To find out the difference in Sense of Humour of Secondary School Teachers with respect to their locality (rural and urban).

3. Hypotheses Of The Study

1. There exists no significant relationship between Teacher Effectiveness of Secondary school teachers with their Sense of Humour.
2. There exists no significant difference in Teacher Effectiveness of Secondary School Teachers with respect to their gender (male and female).
3. There exists no significant difference in Teacher Effectiveness of Secondary School Teachers with respect to their locality (rural and urban).
4. There exists no significant difference in Sense of Humour of Secondary School Teachers with respect to their gender (male and female).
5. There exists no significant difference in Sense of Humour of Secondary School Teachers with respect to their locality (rural and urban).

4. Scope Of The Study

1. The findings of the study had numerous implications that may be useful for the teachers, policy makers and educational policy planners.
2. The present study showed the effect of sense of humour on effective teaching. It helped the school administration and principle to create healthy environment in the school.

3. The study was helpful to promising and aspiring teachers. Their way of teaching should not be monotonous and they should seek active participation of the pupil.

5. Delimitations Of The Study

1. The study was delimited to Uttarkashi District only.
2. The study was delimited to teachers teaching in secondary schools of district Uttarkashi.
3. The study was delimited to one dependent variable i.e. Teacher Effectiveness and on independent variable i.e. Sense of Humour.

6. Methodology Of The Present Study

Research Design: For this research the correlation research design was employed to find the answers of present hypotheses.

6.1 Variables Involved

The independent and dependent variables for the present research were identified as follows:

- Dependent Variable- Teacher Effectiveness
- Independent Variable- Sense of Humour

6.2 Research Method

The present study was conducted by adopting Correlation Research Method of research.

6.3 Population

Secondary school teachers of Uttarkashi District were considered as population of the study.

6.4 Sample & Sampling Technique

The sample for the present study consisted of 200 secondary school teachers (100 Male & 100 Female) of district Uttarkashi.

The data for the present study was collected by using Random Sampling Technique.

6.5 Tools Used

1. Teacher Effectiveness Scale (TES-KU) by Dr. Umme Kulsum (2022).
2. Teacher's Sense of Humour Scale (TSHS) by Malik & Kapoor (2014).

6.6 Statistical Technique

For hypothesis testing, t-test, mean, S.D., Coefficient of correlation Technique was employed to find out the relationship between Teacher Effectiveness & Sense of Humour.

7. Results And Discussion

Regarding the first null hypothesis, it was found after analysis of the data (Table-1) ‘There exists no significant relationship between Teacher Effectiveness of Secondary school teachers with their Sense of Humour.’

Table-1
Relationship between Teacher Effectiveness of Secondary School Teachers with their Sense of Humour

Group	Variables	Value of Coefficient of correlation	Result
Secondary School Teachers	Teacher Effectiveness	+0.407	Positive correlation
	Sense of Humour		

Table 1 Observing the findings displayed in the table, we are in state of asserting that teacher effectiveness and sense of humour is significantly correlated. Hence, the formulated null hypothesis 1, ‘There exists no significant relationship between Teacher Effectiveness of Secondary school teachers with their Sense of Humour’ is rejected.

Table-2
Difference in Teacher Effectiveness of Secondary School Teachers with respect to their gender

Gender	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ value	Level of Confidence
Male	100	544.24	38.17	1.44	Not significant
Female	100	532.76	64.76		

From, table-2 it could be observed that the calculated ‘t’ value of 1.44 at 0.05 level is less than the table value 1.96. Hence, the formulated null hypothesis 2, ‘There exists no significant difference in Teacher Effectiveness of Secondary School Teachers with respect to their gender’ is accepted.

Table-3
Difference in Teacher Effectiveness of Secondary School Teachers with respect to their locality

Locality	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ value	Level of Confidence
Rural	100	550.80	35.59	2.62	Significant
Urban	100	529.96	66.11		

From, table-3 it could be observed that the calculated ‘t’ value of 2.62 at 0.05 level is more than the table value 1.96. Hence, the formulated null hypothesis 3, ‘There exists no significant difference in Teacher Effectiveness of Secondary School Teachers with respect to their Locality’ is rejected.

Table-4

Difference in Sense of Humour of Secondary School Teachers with respect to their gender

Gender	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ value	Level of Confidence
Male	100	187.32	13.95	5.64	Significant
Female	100	173.13	19.94		

From, table-4 it could be observed that the calculated ‘t’ value of 5.64 at 0.05 level is more than the table value 1.96. Hence, the formulated null hypothesis 4, ‘There exists no significant difference in Sense of Humour of Secondary School Teachers with respect to their gender’ is rejected.

Table-5

Difference in Sense of Humour of Secondary School Teachers with respect to their locality

Locality	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ value	Level of Confidence
Rural	100	190.62	11.51	5.35	Significant
Urban	100	179.73	17.83		

From, table- 5 it could be observed that the calculated ‘t’ value of 5.35 at 0.05 level is more than the table value 1.96. Hence, the formulated null hypothesis 5, ‘There exists no significant difference in Sense of Humour of Secondary School Teachers with respect to their Locality’ is rejected.

Similarly, there exists positive relationship between teacher effectiveness and sense of humour of teachers. It is concluded that teachers teaching effectiveness is not influenced by gender and locality. But, the teachers’ sense of humour is influenced by gender and locality.

8. Conclusion

From the above results, it can be concluded that there exists a positive relationship between teacher effectiveness and sense of humor of teachers. it also signifies that teachers’ sense of humor is influenced by gender and locality while teacher effectiveness is not influenced by the same variables i.e. gender and locality. The research emphasizes the holistic development of educators and recognizes the inter- connectedness between teacher effectiveness and their sense of humor. It has the potential to highlight educational policies and practices aiming at the teacher’s well-being, level of humor, thereby benefitting both the teachers and students.

9. Educational Implications

The present study could be beneficial in a lot of ways. Firstly, it indicates the present relationship between teacher effectiveness and teachers' sense of humor, which greatly influences the learning outcomes. This can be helpful in making changes in our teaching style.

In addition to this, the outcome of the present study was found out on the basis of gender and locality, which plays an important role in the learning process. It could be a signifying means to reevaluate our approach towards the zero-gender biasedness in education and the availability of all the important resources required for the attainment for educational objectives irrespective of any locality.

Also, it will be helpful in analysing what other factors could influence the teacher effectiveness and thus the entire teaching-learning process along with gender and locality, so that the required changes could be brought to our education system.

10. Suggestions For Further Research

The present study was carried out between teacher effectiveness of secondary school teachers in relation to their sense of humour. More such study could be carried out between-

- Teacher effectiveness and other variables such as occupational stress, happiness quotient, academic achievement of students, job occupation etc.
- Teacher effectiveness of primary school teachers in relation to their sense of humor.
- Teacher effectiveness of secondary school teachers on the basis of their educational qualifications.
- The present study can be conducted using other methodology.
- Further research can be conducted on large scale.

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